

EGU25-13201, updated on 02 Feb 2026
<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-13201>
EGU General Assembly 2025
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The Digital Twins for Winds-Offshore (DTWO) Project

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What kind of tools are needed for accurate and precise forecasting of offshore wind power, in an unprecedented fast development of offshore wind and market, now and near future, for the key stakeholders?

The DTWO project aims to be pioneering initiative in the digitalization of offshore wind energy by combining

- Federated digital twin architecture, allowing users to customize without sharing sensitive data;
- Seamless model integration of a wide array of existing models and data sources from regional weather model, to wind farm and turbine wakes, to marine environment conditions, to wind resource, energy yield and design parameters, to turbine performance and life time, and to grid balancing and energy market;
- Granular prediction capabilities by implementing latest scientific outcomes and technology;
- High-level cybersecurity, addressing concerns around data vulnerability in digital transformation efforts.

DTWO's federated digital twin platform includes five modules for Earth, Wakes, Siting, Turbines and Grids. DTWO provides a data hub with FAIR and conditionally open data, and a tool hub featuring open and conditionally open tools. The digital twin modules are implemented using industrial use cases, tested through representative test scenarios.

DTWO brings together the expertise of the world's leading offshore wind industries, alongside research centres, IT consulting and digital service providers, academic institutions, a science communication organisation, energy forecasting experts, and meteorological centres. The project website provides more information about the development of the European Horizon supported project <https://dtwo-project.eu/>.

Codes for organizations: 1. DTU; 2. VKI; 3. DHI; 4. ECMWF; 5. SSP; 6. ICONS; 7. PG; 8. Fraunhofer-IWES; 9. ENFOR; 10. KNMI; 11. SGRE

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